

CONSTRUCTION MANUAL

Indirect solar dryer

generation 2

Version 2026.1.7

Compiled by Noah Andreasson on behalf of the SolarFood project

PREFACE

This is a manual that describes how to construct the latest SolarFood solar dryer at the time of publication. It is intended as a practical guide for carpenters, and assumes a basic level of carpentry experience.

The standard capacity of the dryer is around 5-10 kg depending on the crop, but can be scaled up or down as needed by adjusting the dryer dimensions. The dryer itself is an indirect solar dryer, developed and field-tested together with farmers in Bhutan and Nepal over multiple development cycles. See next page for details.

While this manual describes the construction process when using wood as the main body material, the same design can be used for steel-based solar dryers as well. Builders are encouraged to apply their own judgement, and explore different ways of adapting or improving the design as needed to suit local conditions and material availability.

Please note that this manual is provided as-is for informational purposes. SolarFood is not liable for any injury, damage or loss resulting from construction, transportation or use of dryers built using this manual. Dryer performance will also vary depending on factors such as materials used, workmanship, climate conditions and drying load.

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In case of questions, suggestions for improvement or other input, we would be happy to hear from you. Please contact Professor Martin Andersson at martin.andersson@energy.lth.se.

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BACKGROUND

The SolarFood project is an international developmental research collaboration between Lund University (Sweden), Kathmandu University (Nepal), Royal University of Bhutan (Bhutan), and Ruralis (Norway). The aim of the project is to reduce post-harvest losses in Bhutan and Nepal through the development of efficient, affordable and locally adapted solar dryers. The project has been running since 2021, funded by The Swedish Research Council (VR-2020-04071) during 2021-2025, and The Research Council of Norway (project number 352437) during 2026-2028.

The solar dryer design described in this manual is the result of multiple iterative development cycles carried out in close collaboration with local farmers and carpenters in Nepal and Bhutan. Both steel and wooden versions exist. The wooden version is cheaper and easier to construct, and is suitable in non-rainy weather, while the steel version is more suitable for wet climates.

Unlike many other dryers on the market, the indirect solar dryers developed within SolarFood utilise a cheap heat exchanger to recycle heat from the hot, moist air before it leaves the dryer. This significantly increases efficiency of the dryers with only a minor cost increase. The fans are the only components requiring external power, and they draw only a few W in total, which keeps the running costs low. The movement of air through the dryer is illustrated in Figure 1 below.

For further reading, a full list of academic publications resulting from the project is provided on the next page.

Figure 1: A schematic illustration of the second-generation solar dryer. Coloured arrows illustrate the air temperature, where the red end of the colour spectrum corresponds to warmer air.

Research articles

- Andreasson, N., Lundevalle, L., Sonesson, I., Lundquist, M., Dorji, C., Humagai, B.K., Zangmo, P., Baral, B., Davidsson, H. & Andersson, M. (2026). Barriers and drivers for solar dryer adoption in Bhutan and Nepal: A study from the perspective of farmers and producers. *Energy for Sustainable Development* 93, 102024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esd.2026.102024>
- Adhikari, N., Andersson, M., Baral, B. & Garg, H. (2026). Numerical modelling of solar dryers focusing on heat exchangers and solar collectors – comparing flat and rib designs with varying airflows. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering* 80, 107874. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2026.107874>
- Adhikari, N., Garg, H., Davidsson, H., Baral, B. & Andersson, M. (2025). Flow uniformity inside the drying chamber of a heat exchanger-based solar dryer – numerical analysis with smoke flow visualization as experimental validation. *Results in Engineering* 26, 105553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.105553>
- Acharya, A., Davidsson, H., Baral, B. & Andersson, M. (2024) Investigation of thermodynamics performance of a heat exchanger-incorporated solar dryer equipped with double-pass flat, v-corrugated, and low-e coated collectors for drying applications. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering* 64, 105482. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2024.105482>
- Acharya, A., Rissler, C., Baral, B., Lhendup, T., Andersson, M. & Davidsson, H. (2024). Development of a novel solar dryer with an incorporated heat exchanger. *Solar Energy* 269, 112327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2024.112327>

Conference contributions

- Davidsson, H., Jamtsho, T., Om, D. & Andersson, M. (2025). Evaluation of an Indirect Solar Dryer with Integrated Heat Exchanger. In *Proceedings of the EuroSun 2024: ISES and IEA SHC International Conference on Solar Energy for Buildings and Industry in Limassol*, Cyprus International Solar Energy Society. <https://doi.org/10.18086/eurosun.2024.09.03>
- Adhikari, N. & Baral, B. (2025). Numerical Simulation on Thermal Performance of Flat and Rib Heat Exchangers Based Solar Food Dryer Under No Load Conditions. In *IOP Conf. Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 1533, 012032. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1533/1/012032>
- Andreasson, N. & Lundevalle, L. (2025). The Road to Solar Drying: Identifying barriers and drivers for wider adoption of solar dryers in rural Bhutan. *3rd International Conference on Science, Engineering and Technology (ICSciEnTEc 2025)*. Thimphu, Bhutan.

Master's theses and other publications

- Eriksson, A. & Mihajlovic, M. (2026). *Improving Cost-Efficiency of an Indirect Solar Dryer in Nepal* [Master's thesis]. Division of Heat Transfer, Department of Energy Sciences, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University. <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/9221171>
- Andreasson, N. & Lundevalle, L. (2025). *The Road to Improved Solar Drying: Barriers and Drivers for Wider Adoption of Solar Dryers in Rural Bhutan* [Master's thesis]. Division of Heat Transfer, Department of Energy Sciences, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University. <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/9209595>
- Jamtsho, T. & Om, D. (2023). *Design, Analysis and Performance Evaluation of Indirect Solar Dryer* [Master's thesis]. Division of Heat Transfer, Department of Energy Sciences, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University. <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/9141292>
- Müller, L.C. (2024). *Enhancing Post-Harvest Preservation through Improved and Even Solar Drying: A Case Study in Bhutan* [Master's thesis]. Division of Heat Transfer, Department of Energy Sciences, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University. <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/9165837>
- Sörensson, C. (2024). *Simulation and Modelling of Solar Dryer in COMSOL: Analysis of Airflow* [Master's thesis]. Division of Energy and Building Design. Department of Building and Environmental Technology, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University. <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/9151577>
- Küpper, F. (2024). *Solar drying of banana ("Jazi Kela") in the rural area of Bhutan: Engineering and product quality aspects* [Master's thesis]. Division of Food and Pharma, Department of Process and Life Science Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University. <https://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/9167666>
- Mahmoodi, H. (2023). *The Development and Testing of Low-Cost Heat Transfer Enhancements for Solar Dryers* [Master's thesis]. Division of Energy and Building Design, Department of Energy Sciences, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University. <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/9131736>
- Rissler, C. (2023). *Mitigating Post-Harvest Losses in Bhutan through Solar Food Drying: Optimization and Analysis* [Master's thesis]. Division of Energy and Building Design, Department of Building & Environmental Technology, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University. <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/9124967>
- Sonesson, I. & Lundquist, M. (2024). *Barriers and Drivers for Solar Dryer Adoption in Nepal: A Study from Users and Producers Perspectives* [Master's thesis]. Division of Heat Transfer, Department of Energy Sciences, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University. <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/9163921>
- Dorji, J. & Lungten (2023). *Direct solar dryer*. Division of Heat Transfer, Department of Energy Sciences, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University. <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/9141289>
- Karlsson, A. (2022). *Low cost thermal storage for solar dryers in the Himalayas* [Master's thesis]. Division of Heat Transfer, Department of Energy Sciences, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University. <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/9085069>
- Probert, A. (2022). *Development and Testing of a Novel Solar Dryer Design with an Incorporated Heat Exchanger - For use in the Himalayan regions* [Master's thesis]. Division of Heat Transfer, Department of Energy Sciences, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University. <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/9085862>
- Faudot, M.K. (2022). *The impact of induced airflow on the drying process of apples inside a solar drying chamber: A study on food preservation conducted in Nepal* [Master's thesis]. Department of Architecture and Built Environment, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University. <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/907722>
- Otte P.P. (red.), Baral, B., Acharya, A., Yangdon, K., Lhendup, T., Andersson, M., Andersson, E. & Davidsson, H. (2022). *A need assessment for designing sustainable solar drying technology in Nepal and Bhutan*. Ruralis report (R-8/22), Trondheim. <https://ruralis.no/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/r-8-22-a-need-assessment-for-designing-sustainable-solar-drying-technology-in-nepal-and-bhutan-p-otte-et-al.pdf>
- Fremstad, J.J. (2022). *Better drying techniques can reduce food waste*. <https://ruralis.no/en/2022/11/02/better-drying-techniques-can-reduce-food-waste/>

REQUIREMENTS

Materials needed

Type	Quantity	Length	Width	Thickness
Wooden sheet	3	244 cm (8 ft)	122 (4 ft)	1 cm
Wooden beam	5	240 cm	5 cm	5 cm
Glass panel	1	132 cm	100 cm	5 mm
PGI sheet (for solar collector)	1	110 cm	100 cm	1 mm
Plastic or metal sheet (for heat exchanger)	1	100 cm	100 cm	1 mm
Aluminium wire mesh	1 roll	3 m	1 m	
AC blower fan	1	15 cm	15 cm	
AC internal fan	1	10 cm	10 cm	
Black enamel paint	250 ml			
Adhesive	1 tube			
Sealing tape or silicone sealant	1 roll or 1 flask			
Screws	1 package			
Nails	1 package			
Angle bracket	Up to 26			
Insulation (<i>optional</i>)	Up to 4 sheets	100 cm	100 cm	5 cm
Wheels (<i>optional</i>)	4			
Door hinges, hooks, or other method of attaching door	Depends on method			

See Appendix 1 for a suggestion on how to efficiently cut the wooden sheets and beams.

Tools needed

- Screwdriver
- Drill
- Hammer
- Saw
- Paint brush
- Tape measure or folding rule
- Pencil

PART 1: STAND

Step 1.1: Make four beams: two with a length of 100 cm, and two with a length of 90 cm. All four should have a width of 5 × 5 cm.

Step 1.2: Create a 1 × 1 meter square, and connect them using screws or nails:

Step 1.3: Create four 30 cm long (5 × 5 cm wide) legs:

Step 1.4: Connect them to the square using screws, to make a stand:

Important: Make sure that the screws are strong and tight. They must be able to support the weight of the dryer.

Optional: Use angle brackets around the legs to further support the weight:

Optional: If wheels are desired, now is a good time to attach wheels under the legs.

PART 2: BOTTOM & HEAT EXCHANGER

Step 2.1: Cut a thin piece of wood (thickness of 1 cm) into a 1 × 1 meter square.

Step 2.2: Cut a small circular hole in the middle, close to the edge. Approximately 15 cm diameter.

Step 2.3: Use screws or nails to attach the plate to the stand.

Note: In this manual, the stand/legs are sometimes hidden from illustrations to save space.

Step 2.4: Cut a 100 cm long (5 × 5 cm wide) beam into a triangle:

Step 2.5: Screw or nail the triangular beam to the end of the bottom plate.

Step 2.6: Cut a thin (1 cm thickness) piece of wood into three 90 × 5 cm planks:

Step 2.7: Fasten the planks on the edges on top of the bottom plate:

Step 2.8: Make six thin (1 cm thickness) 5 × 10 cm pieces:

Step 2.9: Fasten into two rows on the bottom plate, evenly spread:

Step 2.10: Make eight 2 × 20 cm pieces (1 cm thickness):

Step 2.11: Fasten on the bottom plate, evenly spread and rotated:

Step 2.12: Glue or tape the heat exchanger material on top. You can use thin plastic or metal.

Important: Make sure that it does not sag, and that it is airtight on all edges except the one facing the triangular beam. The air must be able to flow underneath the material.

Step 2.13: Make five 1 cm thick pieces: one 100 × 5 cm, and four 90 × 5 cm.

Step 2.14: Fasten the 100 cm long piece in the front.

Step 2.15: Fasten the four 90 cm long pieces.

If you use plastic as heat exchanger material, the result should now look similar to this:

Step 2.16: Attach a blower fan to the underside of the bottom plate, under the hole.

Important: The blower fan must be placed so that it sucks air from the bottom, and blows it up into the dryer (the direction of the arrow) when plugged in.

Step 2.17: Make a 100 × 80 cm thin (1 cm thickness) plate.

Step 2.18: Place the new plate on top, leaving space on the side of the triangular beam:

Step 2.19: Make a 100 × 10 cm thin (1 cm thickness) plank:

Step 2.20: Cut three holes into the plank (around 26 cm wide):

Step 2.21: Use the cut plank to finish the top, leaving three holes:

It should now look like this:

PART 3: BODY FRAME

Step 3.1: Make five beams. All should have a width of 5×5 cm.

- Two with a length of 80 cm
- Three with a length of 90 cm

Step 3.2: Take two of the 90 cm long beams and make a diagonal cut at the end:

Step 3.3: Attach the beams. The 80 cm long ones in the front, the 90 cm long in the back.

Important: Secure the frame strongly to the rest of the dryer using multiple screws (and preferably angle brackets), as shown in the picture:

Photo: Tandlin Jamtsho

Step 3.4: Cut a 100 cm long (5 × 5 cm wide) beam into a triangular shape:

Step 3.5: Attach the triangle in the front to the rest of the frame.

PART 4: SOLAR COLLECTOR AND BACK WALL

Step 4.1: Make a 100 × 80 cm thin (1 cm thickness) plate.

Step 4.2: Attach it to the beams in the back.

Step 4.3: Make a thin (1 cm thickness) 100 × 127.5 cm plate.

Step 4.4: Create a 2 × 90 cm hole, around 10 cm from the right edge.

Step 4.5: Attach it to both the front and back beams using screws or nails:

Step 4.6: Make two thin (1 cm thickness) 5 × 127.5 cm planks:

Step 4.7: Attach to the edges of the roof using adhesive, nails or screws.

Step 4.8: Prepare a 100 × 110 cm thin metal sheet and paint it black.
(Example: 1 mm thick PGI sheet with black enamel paint)

Step 4.9: Attach the metal sheet to the planks on both sides of the roof using adhesive.

Note: leave some space (3-4 cm) in the bottom of the roof, see picture:

Step 4.10: Make two thin (1 cm thickness) 5 × 127.5 cm planks:

Step 4.11: Attach to the edges of the roof, on top of the metal plate.

Note: Use screws to attach the planks firmly both above and below the metal plate, in order to pin it securely to the roof.

Step 4.12: Cut a 90 × 9.5 cm plank. Thickness should be around 2 cm. If necessary, you can put two 1 cm thick planks together.

Step 4.13: Attach it to the top of the roof. Do not cover the hole you cut during step 4.4.

PART 5: DRYING CHAMBER

Step 5.1: Make a 100 × 49 cm thin (1 cm thickness) plate.

Step 5.2: Cut a small circular hole in the middle, close to the top. Approximately 10 cm diameter.

Step 5.3: Place it in the middle of the drying chamber, leaving 29 cm of space to the back wall. Secure it to the frame using iron angles.

Important note: The top of this new wall should touch the roof, but rest on the dryer frame beams from step 3.3. There must be space between this wall and the chamber floor to allow airflow.

Step 5.4: Make 2 thin (1 cm thickness) 20 × 2 cm pieces:

Step 5.5: Attach them to the roof to keep the separator wall in place.

Step 5.6: Make a 100 × 22 cm thin (1 cm thickness) plate.

Step 5.7: Cut away a 5 × 5 cm square from the two bottom corners.

Step 5.8: Place it close to the front in the drying chamber, leaving 29 cm of space to the middle wall. Secure it to the frame using iron angles.

Important note: This wall should rest on the chamber floor, and instead leave space above (between the wall and the roof). See next page:

Photo: Tandin Jamtscho. Edited.

Step 5.9: Create eighteen shelf pieces. They should be 90 cm long, 1-1.5 cm tall, and around 1 cm wide.

Step 5.10: Create shelves by attaching the pieces to the inner walls using screws or nails. They should all be 5 cm apart. Make 3 shelves in the left chamber, and 6 in the right chamber.

Step 5.11 (optional, but recommended): Attach mesh between the left inner wall and the roof, for example using small nails or staples. This will help prevent crops from accidentally spilling over the edge into a space that is hard to reach once the dryer is assembled.

Note: It is important to use mesh or something else that lets air through easily. Do not use solid material or cloth.

Step 5.12: Attach a small inner fan on top of the hole in the chamber using screws.

Important: The fan must be placed so that it blows air towards the back of the dryer (the direction of the arrow) when plugged in.

Photo: Tandim Jamtsho

Step 5.13: Lead the fan cable away from the shelves, and out from the dryer. Use tape or a small nail to keep the cable close to the roof and frame.

Step 5.14: Measure the final distance between the walls using a tape measure or a folding rule.

PART 6: DRYING TRAYS

Step 6.1: Make eighteen 1 cm thick, 3 cm tall pieces. The length should be **0.5-1 cm less** than the distance between the walls (measured in step 5.14).

*(If the distances were different, make 6 pieces using length **a**, and 12 pieces using length **b**)*

For example, if the distance between the walls is 29 cm, these pieces should be 28-28.5 cm long.

Step 6.2: Make eighteen 88 × 3 cm pieces, 1 cm thick.

Step 6.3: Connect them together using small nails or screws into nine rectangles.

Step 6.4: Add mesh to the underside of each tray. Connect the mesh using, for example, staples or small nails.

Photo: Noah Andreasson

Note: It is important to use mesh or something else that lets air through easily. Do not use solid material or cloth.

PART 7: GLASS PANEL AND OUTER WALLS

Step 7.1: Place the 100 × 132 cm glass panel carefully on top of the dryer.

Important: The glass should rest against the first triangular beam that you prepared in step 2.4:

Step 7.2: Use tape or sealant all around the glass to help secure it in place, and to protect the dryer against water seepage.

BACK

SIDE

FRONT

Step 7.3: Prepare a 100 × 100 cm square from a thin piece of wood (thickness of 1 cm).

Step 7.4: Cut the square diagonally.

Step 7.5: Attach one of them to the left side of the dryer using screws.

Note: be careful with the fan cable. You can either:

- Make a small cut or drilling to make room for the cable, OR
- Leave a small space between the frame and the outer wall. If you do this, patch up the hole with sealant or tape to make the chamber airtight.

Step 7.6: Measure the distance between the front and the first separator wall in the chamber using a tape measure or a folding rule.

Step 7.7: Use the length from step 7.6, and cut the other triangle you made during step 7.4.

Step 7.8: Attach it to the right side of the dryer using screws.

Step 7.9: Cut out a 24 cm triangle from the remaining piece.

Step 7.10: Attach the small part to the dryer, on top of the right side.

Optional: cut away the top edge.

Step 7.11: The final piece is the door, and fits the right side of the dryer. There are many ways to attach a door. You can hang it on hooks, use hinges, etc. We leave this design decision up to you.

PART 8: FINAL TOUCHES

Step 8.1: Insert the trays.

Step 8.2 (optional, recommended in very cold climates): Depending on the needs in your area, it might be beneficial to add thermal insulation to the outer walls. It increases solar dryer performance in cold temperatures, but is not necessary in hotter climates.

Step 8.3: This is important! Use sealant or plastic tape to cover seams, cracks and small, unintended openings in the dryer. This keeps water out from the dryer, hot air inside for longer, and improves dryer performance. It also has the added benefit of making the dryer more robust.

APPENDIX 1: Suggestions for efficient cutting of wooden beams and sheets

Suggestion for beam cut plan:

Beam 1 (240 cm): 100 + 80 + 30 + 30

Beam 2 (220 cm): 100 + 90 + 30

Beam 3 (220 cm): 100 + 90 + 30

Beam 4 (200 cm): 90 + 80 + 30

Beam 5 (190 cm): 100 + 90

Suggestion for sheet cut plan:

244×122 cm sheets (8×4 ft)

Sheet 1:

Pieces on sheet 1 (12 total)

■ 100×100 ■ 5×10 ■ 100×5 ■ 100×10 ■ 100×127.5 ■ 5×127.5 ■ 90×9.5 (×2) ■ 28.5×3 (×4)

Sheet 2:

Pieces on sheet 2 (21 total)

■ 100×100 ■ 90×5 (×7) ■ 5×10 (×3) ■ 100×80 ■ 5×127.5 (×3) ■ 100×22 ■ 90×1
■ 28.5×3 (×3) ■ 88×3

Sheet 3:

Pieces on sheet 3 (59 total)

■ 5×10 (×2) ■ 2×20 (×10) ■ 100×80 ■ 100×49 ■ 90×1 (×17) ■ 28.5×3 (×11) ■ 88×3 (×17)